

Determination of praseodymium in mixed rare earths by norfloxacin

Nai-Xing Wang*, Xue-Zheng Ren, Chuen-Bo Liu, Zhi-Kun Si, Wei Jiang and Xiao-Lu Liu

Department of Chemistry, Shandong University, Jinan, 250100, People's Republic of China

Manuscript received 4 January 1999, revised 17 May 1999, accepted 20 May 1999

A method is described for the derivative spectrophotometric determination of trace amounts of praseodymium as its complex with norfloxacin. The absorption bands of *4f*-electron transitions of praseodymium complex with norfloxacin are enhanced markedly. Using the second derivative spectra, the calibration graph is linear over the range 5–35 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-3}$ of Pr. The method has been successfully used for the determination of Pr in mixed rare earths.

It is well-known that the absorption spectra of rare earth ions consisting of narrow bands due to electronic transitions (Laporte forbidden) within the f^n -configuration, are affected only slightly by changes in the environment around the metal ion. However, if the strength of the ionic field surrounding the rare earth ions is sufficient to penetrate the shielding, some absorption bands may be shifted to different wavelength and with enhanced sensitivity¹. There are reports on the derivative spectrophotometric determination of complexes formed by rare earths with β -diketones,² 8-hydroxyquinoline³ and its derivatives⁴. However, so far there are only a few reports dealing with the determination of Pr in rare earth mixtures⁵ and its alloys⁶ based on the absorption bands of *4f*-electron transitions of Pr.

Norfloxacin [1-ethyl-6-fluoro-7-(1-piperaziny)-4-oxo-1,4-dihydro-3-quinoline carboxylic acid, NFX] is a fluorinated quinoline antibiotic, which possesses a carboxylic acid moiety and the carbonyl group required for antimicrobial activity and that is also thought to be a site of chelation interaction with various cations. Here we report a second derivative spectrophotometric method for the direct determination of trace amounts of Pr in a mixture of rare earths using its complex with NFX.

Results and Discussion

Fig. 1 shows the zero and second derivative of Pr^{III} and its complex with NFX. As the characteristic peaks of the complex are almost at the same wavelengths as those of the free ion (PrCl_3), the absorption bands of complex at 470 and 482 nm are attributed to $^3H_4 \rightarrow ^3I_6 + ^3P_1, ^3P_0$ transition of praseodymium. The bands are changed as a result of the ligands affecting the coordination field. A sharp *4f*-electron transition band (at 482 nm) allows its determination by means of the derivative spectra.

We investigated the 1st-4th derivative spectra of different lanthanide complexes and variable measuring parameters of the instrument. The optimum instrumental parameters are given in Experimental. Fig. 2 shows the second derivative spectra of the representative lanthanide

Fig. 1. Zero order and second order derivative spectra of ion and complex: $[\text{Pr}] = 1.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{NFX}] = 7.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, pH = 8.8 : (1) Pr (pH = 5.6) against water as reference and (2,2') Pr-NFX against reagent blank as reference.

complexes. It is obvious that the optimal analytical signals are at 480.5(+) nm peak and 482.5(–) nm valley for praseodymium complex, because the other rare earth complexes do not have second derivative bands corresponding to *4f*-electron transitions in this wavelength range.

From the second derivative absorption of a $1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ Pr solution with $7.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ NFX, the maximum absorption was obtained in the pH range 8.0–9.5. Therefore, a pH 8.8 buffer solution was selected. The absorption for Pr complex at second derivative spectrum reached a maximum and constant absorbance when $2.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ of NFX was employed, and then remained constant. The complex was formed in 10 min and the derivative absorption signal was stable for at least 5.0 h.

The calibration graph from the second derivative spectra of the complex obeyed Beer's law up to $35 \mu\text{g cm}^{-3}$ of Pr (in the final solution). The equation obtained by the least-squares method was

$$d^2A/d\lambda^2 = 0.0023 [\text{Pr}] - 0.0038$$

$$r = 0.9993 \quad (n = 5)$$

where c is the concentration ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-3}$) and γ the correlation coefficient.

The effect of other ions on the absorption signals of praseodymium complex was studied. At 1.0×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} of praseodymium, the highest molar excess that caused $\pm 5.0\%$ of variation was as follows: other lanthanide ions (40-fold), Zn^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} (100-fold); Ga^{III} , In^{III} , Sn^{IV} (30-fold); Fe^{III} , Mn^{II} (10-fold).

Fig. 2. Second derivative spectra of the lanthanide complexes; $[\text{Ln}] = 1.5 \times 10^{-4}$ mol dm^{-3} , $\Delta\lambda = 1.0$ nm, bandpass = 1.0 nm, scan-rate = 20 nm min^{-1} (other conditions as in Fig. 1): (1) Pr, (2) La, (3) Er, (4) Nd, (5) Y and (6) Ce^{IV} .

Application: In order to test the utility of the method, two reference materials and one lanthanide base sample were analysed for praseodymium. The procedure is as follows. The reference material (or sample) (~ 0.5 g) dissolved in HCl (1 : 1; 10 cm^3) was heated and evaporated nearly to dryness on a water-bath, then the residue was dissolved in water and diluted to 100 cm^3 with water. An aliquot (0.50–1.0 cm^3) of the solution was diluted to 10 cm^3 and the Pr content determined by the above procedure. The results are listed in Table 1.

Conclusion: The proposed method involves the use of the second derivative spectra for the praseodymium complex with NFX. The method is not very sensitive, but it is simple, rapid and selective in the presence of other rare earth elements.

Experimental

Standard solutions (0.05 mol dm^{-3}) of lanthanides were prepared by dissolving their oxides (Johnson Mathey) in HCl (1 : 1) and working solutions were prepared by dilution with water. An aqueous solution (0.05 mol dm^{-3}) of NFX (99.85% purity) was prepared. Buffer solution of pH

8.8 was prepared using 1.0 mol dm^{-3} of ammonia and ammonium chloride.

A Shimadzu UV-240 spectrophotometer with 4.0 cm cells was used. Derivative spectra were obtained with a Shimadzu derivative spectrum attachment optional program/interface model OP1-2 (1st to 4th derivative, $\Delta\lambda$ 1, 2 and 4 nm). The pH was measured with a pHs-2 meter.

Table 1. Analytical results for Pr in reference materials and lanthanide sample*

Sample no.	Oxides present (%)	Pr found (%)			
		Present work	RSD ^a	XRF ^b	RSD ^c
1 ^c	La, 27.11; Ce^{IV} , 49.21; Pr, 5.18; Nd, 16.75; Sm, 1.29; Eu, 0.23; Gd, 0.40; Tb, 0.03; Dy, 0.09; Y, 0.27; Ho, 0.023; Er, 0.027; Tm, 0.0095; Yb, 0.013; Lu, 0.003	5.02	2.3	5.06	2.1
2 ^c	La, 13.83; Ce^{IV} , 62.98; Pr, 5.76; Nd, 14.43; Sm, 1.83; Eu, 0.25; Gd, 0.42; Tb, 0.027; Dy, 0.077; Ho, 0.019; Er, 0.022; Tm, 0.0076; Yb, 0.015; Lu, 0.0001; Y, 0.045	5.62	2.4	5.76	1.2
3 ^d	La, 23.10; Ce^{IV} , 0.90; Pr, 7.31; Nd, 21.53; Sm, 2.21; Gd, 3.24; Tb, 0.32; Y, 5.25; Ho, 0.98; Er, 0.30; Yb, 0.24	7.17	1.9	7.25	2.0

* Average of six determinations.

^aRelative standard deviation ($n = 6$). ^bX-ray fluorescence method. ^cFrom Baotou Rare Earths Academy, China. ^dFrom Jiangxi Xiunwu Lanthanide material sample, China.

Procedure: A mixture of a known volume of the lanthanide solution, 0.05 mol dm^{-3} of NFX (3 ml) and buffer solution (3 ml) was diluted to 10 cm^3 with distilled water. The solution was allowed to stand for 10 min and the second derivative spectra were recorded against a reagent blank as reference using $\Delta\lambda = 1.0$ nm, bandpass = 1.0 nm scan-rate = 20 nm min^{-1} . The amplitudes were measured at 480.5(+) and 482.5(-) nm for Pr.

Acknowledgement

This work was financially supported by the State Education Commission of China.

References

1. T. Taketatsus and N. Toyiumi, *Talanta*, 1970, **17**, 465.
2. J. W. Kang, R.-Y. Chen and G.-B. Beri, *Huaxue Xuebao*, 1984, **42**, 921 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1984, **101**, 203517).
3. N.-X. Wang, W.-A. Liang and Z.-Z. Zhang, *Analyst*, 1992, **117**, 1963.
4. N.-X. Wang, Q.-C. Wu, J.-B. Shi and P. Qi, *Mikrochim Acta*, 1993, **110** 119.
5. H. Ishji and K. Satoh, *Bunseki Kagaku*, 1986, **35**, 704 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1986, **105**, 182944).
6. Y. Ren and Y.-L. Tong, *Yingyong Huaxue*, 1987, **4**, 55 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1988, **108**, 87126).